

Knowledge and Expectation

What do I know about (data) literacy?

What do you know about ethics?

What would you like learn/discuss?

Media literacy and some aspects of its ethics

How to establish data literacy as basic knowledge in engineering?

Which aspects I have to keep in mind when it comes to ethical aspects in engineering?

Are there any ethical aspects when working with machine data only?

What is ethics for data? +1

Measurement techniques

Write your name next to a dot and place it on the scala.

[Participant Name]

[Participant Name]

[Participant Name]

Mario

[Participant Name]

[Jan]

[Ina]

[Manuela]

[Participant Name]

Satish

Literacy Circles

forget the umbrella and try dancing in the rain instead

Write your comment to the presented literacy concept.

Start Burst Brainstorming

When you think about ethical questions in data literacy.
What have you come across so far?

Please, generate ethical questions in the context of data literacy

Take one Star point and start generating ethical questions with the question word (What...)

Feedback

interesting view on RDM and data literacy

good mix of interactivity and presentations

That was good

the concept of the workshop

new insights

That was not good

Too short :(

That was new to me

